

STAGES OF WORD FORMATION IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH LANGUAGES

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Abstract: This scientific article examines the stages of word formation in Uzbek and English languages. It can be seen that the interpretation of word formation as a lexical phenomenon has become more widespread in English linguistics. Any new approach in the field of linguistics cannot be perfected in a short period of time, and in turn, any innovation implemented cannot be considered absolutely perfect. A specific proof of this can be observed in the example of the interpretation of word formation sometimes as a morphological, sometimes as a lexical phenomenon.

Keywords: linguistics, Uzbek and foreign languages, word formation, system, stages

The first stage of word formation is distinguished as a "morphological stage" in the sources of general linguistics. The morphological tradition formed at this stage continued consistently until the middle of the last century in the research on word formation. In particular, in the guide to the Uzbek language created by Abdurauf Fitrat at the beginning of the last century, as well as by A.N. In the textbooks published by scientists like Kononov and V.V. Reshetov, the influence of this tradition that arose in the history of linguistics can be observed.

In particular, it can be observed that word formation is recognized as a phenomenon with its own laws in some cases. In particular, the following opinion expressed by A.M. Shcherbak is an example of this: "There is a relatively

independent internal phenomenon in word groups that does not fully obey morphological laws"1. According to A.M.Shcherbak, word formation is distinguished by the creation of secondary bases in word groups. The concept of the secondary base is directly related to word formation, and they are formed by means of word-forming affixes. Although we cannot say that this opinion of A. M. Shcherbak caused a radical change in the interpretation of the phenomenon of word formation, it is worthy of attention as one of the leading views of its time on the fact that word formation is a separate phenomenon in the language.

In one of the articles published in the 1950s by A. Gulomov, who was one of the first in Uzbek linguistics to conduct a special study based on word formation, the following information can be found about the current state of word formation research: "We consider the issue of word formation so far we have been looking at it morphologically, whereas word formation is the creation of a new word in some way. So, it belongs to the lexicon - word debate. According to the old grammar theory, word formation and word change were considered in morphology. In reality, these are formally similar but functionally different phenomena: the first is a lexical phenomenon, the second is a syntactic phenomenon," he wrote.

It can be seen that the interpretation of word formation as a lexical phenomenon has become more widespread in English linguistics. In particular, in works on lexicology published by A.I. Smirnitsky, T.I.Arbekova, word formation was studied together with other lexical phenomena. Of course, any new approach created in science cannot be perfected in a short period of time and in one way, in turn, any innovation implemented cannot be considered absolutely perfect. A specific proof of this can be observed in the example of the interpretation of word formation sometimes as a morphological, sometimes as a lexical phenomenon.

Perception and scientific justification of the fact that the phenomenon of word formation is different from morphological forms is one of the conclusions that emerged as a result of multi-stage, continuous research. The factors that led linguists to recognize word formation as one of the special events in language

cannot be attributed to recent history. Already, the initial theoretical views on the formation of words began to have their origin, on the one hand, with the discussion of linguistic and philosophical issues of the language, and on the other hand, as a result of the accumulated experiences in the study of the word and its morphological structure.

By the 60s of the history of linguistics, these rich experiences accumulated in the study of word formation were further deepened based on the laws related to the morphological, phonetic phonological, lexical-semantic, and syntactic layers of the language. In particular, G.O. Vinokur, N.A. Yanko-Trinskaya, A.N. Tikhonov, Ye.S.Kubryakova, V.V.Lopatin, I.S.Ulukhanov, N.M.Shansky, etc. played an important role in scientific research, while in Uzbek linguistics U.Tursunov, Z.Marupov, The scientific researches of A. Ghulomov, A. Madraximov, B. Madaliyev, A. Hojiyev, etc. have become of special importance.

Consequently, thanks to the efforts of these scientists, the phenomena of formation manifested in the word structure, firstly, were distinguished from the special signs related to the formation of the form, and secondly, the occurrence of word formation based on the unique structural-semantic possibilities of its different levels in the language conclusions began to emerge that it is a phenomenon that develops in harmony with A similar situation can be observed in the grammar of the Korean language, which began to acquire its perfect form in the 70s of the last century.

Another direction in the linguistic interpretations of the phenomenon of word formation is highlighted by the study of this phenomenon under the term derivation. This term was introduced into linguistics in the 60s of the last century by the Czech linguist E. Kurilovich. He uses the term derivation in order to respond to the opinion of the German linguist Slotti about the factors that are important in determining the proportionality and disproportion of semantic category and syntactic function in word groups.

In fact, specific proofs of this can be found in the "Annotated Dictionary of

Linguistic Terms" published after the second half of the last century. can also be seen in the example. Scientific views on the formation of compound words were also interpreted based on the ideas put forward at these stages, which require a specific historical stage of word formation.

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